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Donor Properties of Ditertiaryphosphine Dioxides towards Iron(III)

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COORDINATION chemistry of bifunctional organophosphorus ligands, namely, ditertiaryphosphine dioxides towards various metal ions has been reported¹. However, there are known only two complexes with iron(III), viz., [Fe(MBDPO)₂](ClO₄)₃ and [Fe(MBDPO)₂][FeCl₄]₃ (MBDPO = 1,1-methylenebis(dibutylphosphine oxide)). It was therefore considered worthwhile to study the coordination properties of bidentate ditertiaryphosphine dioxides (I) involving phenyl substituents on phosphorus towards iron(II) and iron(III).

The intention was to study the effect of ring size on stability and nature of complexes by increasing the number of methylene groups and using Mössbauer spectrometer as one of techniques for structure elucidation. In this communication, we are reporting complexes of 1,1-methylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (MDPO), 1,2-dimethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (EDPO), 1,4-tetramethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (BDPO) and 1,6-hexamethylenebis(diphenylphosphine oxide) (HDPO) with chloride, bromide, nitrate and perchlorate of iron(III). These have been characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, ir and reflectance spectra.

Experimental

The ligands MDPO, EDPO, BDPO and HDPO were prepared by oxidation of the corresponding ditertiaryphosphines with hydrogen peroxide (Lit. m.p. MDPO, 176-178°; EDPO, 256-58°; BDPO, 246-47° and HDPO, 196-97°)².

The complexes were prepared by the interaction of iron(III) salts with the ligands in suitable solvents. The solid products were obtained either on gentle heating or on subsequent treatment with petroleum ether (40-60°). Iron was estimated spectrophotometrically³. Carbon and hydrogen were analysed in University College of Sciences, Calcutta. The molar conductances of millimolar solutions of complexes in nitrobenzene were measured with Toshniwal Type CLOI/02A conductivity bridge. The ir spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in the range 4600-650 cm⁻¹ in nujol mulls using Spectromom-2000. The reflectance spectra of the complexes in the range

TABLE 1—THE ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND SPECTRAL PROPERTIES OF COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Analysis % ; Found, (Calcd.)			m.p. (°C)	$\nu(\text{PO})$ cm ⁻¹	λ_{max} nm
		C	H	Fe			
1.	FeCl ₃ .MDPO	50.80 (51.80)	4.39 (3.91)	10.43 (9.68)	268	1145 (s, sp) 1140 (w)	330 (m, sp), 430 (b, s), 520 (sh)
2.	FeCl ₃ .BDPO	55.53 (54.10)	5.08 (4.50)	8.82 (9.02)	212	1146 (s, sp) 1162 (s, sp)	360 (sh), 380 (s, sp), 400 (w)
3.	FeCl ₃ .HDPO.H ₂ O	54.32 (54.01)	5.19 (5.10)	8.31 (8.40)	112	1139 (s, sp)	360 (sh), 380 (s, sp), 430 (s, sp), 400 (w)
4.	[Fe(MDPO) ₂](ClO ₄) ₃ .H ₂ O	54.58 (55.53)	3.90 (4.19)	3.75 (3.45)	300	1172 (m, sp)	350 (s, sp), 510 (w, b)
5.	[Fe(EDPO) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ [(ClO ₄) ₂]	51.86 (50.62)	4.09 (4.05)	4.52 (4.54)	262	1.38 (s, sp)	330 (sh), 360 (s, sp)
6.	[Fe(BDPO)(ac) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ .ClO ₄	44.46 (43.90)	3.48 (3.60)	6.18 (6.39)	210(d)	1170 (s, sp)	350 (s, sp), 370 (sh)
7.	[Fe ₂ (MDPO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₄].[NO ₃] ₂ .2H ₂ O	50.14 (50.81)	4.65 (3.95)	6.52 (6.33)	221(d)	1154 (s, sp) 1170 (m, sp)	370 (sh), 390 (s, sp), 490 (w), 570 (w)
8.	[Fe(EDPO) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂].[NO ₃].H ₂ O	55.10 (55.71)	3.54 (4.46)	5.49 (5.00)	264	1140 (s, sp) 1170 (sh)	380 (s, sp), 430 (w), 460 (s, sp)
9.	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .BDPO	47.43 (48.00)	—	3.40 (3.00)	121	1134 (s, sp)	380 (s, sp), 430 (w), 460 (s, sp)
10.	FeBr ₃ .BDPO	44.01 (44.50)	3.46 (3.60)	7.96 (7.42)	206	1139 (s, sp) 1150 (s, sp)	380 (sh), 420 (w), 490 (s, sp), 540 (w)

d = decomposition ; s = strong ; m = medium ; sp = sharp ; sh = shoulder ; w = weak ; ac = acetone.

The ir spectra show the presence of lattice water in complexes.

300-700 nm were recorded with spectrophotometer VSU-2P.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) show the formation of complexes of stoichiometries; 1:1, 1:2, 2:3 and 1:3 (metal:ligand). The colours of complexes range from white to yellow to red. The melting points of complexes fall in the range of melting points of their respective ligands except those of HDPO. The molar conductance values of chloride complexes of MDPO, BDPO and HDPO indicate them to be essentially non-electrolytes (Δ 10.92, 15.95 and 15.32 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively). Similarly, the perchlorate complexes are formulated as, $[\text{Fe}(\text{MDPO})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{EDPO})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{BDPO})(\text{ClO}_4)_2(\text{ac})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ (Δ 67.36, 56.36, 32.80 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively). The nitrate complex of MDPO is a 2:3 electrolyte and that of EDPO is a 1:1 electrolyte (Δ 48.01 and 20.40 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively) which are formulated as $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{MDPO})_3(\text{NO}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{EDPO})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2](\text{NO}_3)$. However, the corresponding BDPO complex is a non-electrolyte (Δ 9.76 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$) and is analogous to complex of BDPO with iron(III) chloride.

The phosphoryl stretching frequencies in MDPO and EDPO appear as doublets at 1205, 1192 and 1190, 1180 cm^{-1} , respectively while in BDPO and HDPO as singlets at 1182, 1185 cm^{-1} , respectively (Table 1). The $\nu(\text{PO})$ bands appear in the range 1172-1128 cm^{-1} in the complexes either as a singlet or a doublet. There is negative spectral shift of *ca* 22-52 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$ indicating that metal-ligand interaction takes place through phosphoryl group. The reflectance spectra is characteristic of iron(III) complexes⁴⁻⁵ and λ_{max} falls in the range 330-645 nm (Table 1). Detailed studies on these as well as a number of related complexes are in progress.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Sulphaphenazole Complexes with La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

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In the present investigation, potentiometric studies have been carried out on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole and its complexes with some trivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphaphenazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised to obtain an analytically pure compound with m. p. 226°.

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid of A.R. Grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details were the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the course of titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 hr. This was further confirmed by taking tlc of a sample titration mixture from time to time.

In the ligand, it is the phenolic-OH group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by the metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and the formation curve (B vs $\bar{n}_A$) was plotted. The pK_1^H corresponding to phenolic H was obtained by half integral method at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$. This was further corroborated by plotting the graph of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B.